

Comparative Study of Efficacy between Platelet-Rich Plasma Injections versus Ultrasound Therapy in Treating Lateral Epicondylitis

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Abstract:

This study investigated the efficacy of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections and ultrasound therapy in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis. The research was conducted on a group of 60 patients at the Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Patna Medical College and Hospital, from April 2022 to October 2023. The study results indicated that PRP injections were found to be more effective in reducing pain and enhancing functional outcomes when compared to ultrasound therapy. It is worth mentioning that the PRP group experienced higher levels of patient satisfaction. The results presented in this study offer compelling evidence supporting the efficacy of PRP injections in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis. In comparison to traditional ultrasound therapy, PRP injections provide enhanced clinical advantages. This study contributes to the growing body of evidence that supports the application of regenerative medicine techniques in the treatment of musculoskeletal disorders.

Keywords: Lateral Epicondylitis, Platelet-Rich Plasma, Ultrasound Therapy, Regenerative Medicine.

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Introduction

Tennis elbow, or lateral epicondylitis, is a frequently encountered issue that results in discomfort and sensitivity on the outer part of the elbow [1]. This condition is often associated with overexertion of the muscles and tendons in the forearm, leading to tendinopathy of the extensor carpi radialis brevis [2]. While it mainly affects athletes who engage in racquet sports, it is also prevalent among individuals with jobs that require repetitive wrist and arm movements [3]. There are several approaches to treating lateral epicondylitis. These include taking regular breaks, participating in physical therapy, taking nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and receiving corticosteroid injections [4]. However, these treatments often provide temporary relief and may have limitations in terms of their effectiveness and potential side effects. Consequently, there is a growing interest in alternative therapies that provide long-lasting advantages with minimal adverse effects [5].

Among the various options available, Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections and ultrasound therapy have demonstrated significant potential. PRP therapy involves injecting concentrated platelets from the patient's blood into the affected area to enhance the healing process [6]. Contrary to

popular belief, ultrasound therapy utilizes sound waves to promote tissue healing and reduce pain through a combination of thermal and non-thermal effects [7]. The objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the efficacy of PRP injections and ultrasound therapy as potential treatments for lateral epicondylitis [8]. The study seeks to evaluate and compare the outcomes of these treatments in terms of pain reduction, functional improvement, and overall patient satisfaction. This research provides evidence-based guidance for selecting between different therapies, which could have a significant impact on clinical practices for managing lateral epicondylitis [9].

Methodology

The study was conducted as a comparative clinical trial at the Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Patna Medical College and Hospital, from April 2022 to October 2023. A total of 60 patients diagnosed with lateral epicondylitis were enrolled in the study following a thorough screening process to ensure they met the inclusion criteria.

Participant Selection: Patients with lateral epicondylitis confirmed by clinical examination and ultrasound imaging, age 18–60, and symptoms

lasting more than three months were included. Patients having past elbow surgery, local infection, systemic inflammatory disorders, or elbow injections within six months were excluded.

Study Design: The 60 participants were randomly assigned into two groups, with 30 patients in each group. Group A received Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections, and Group B underwent ultrasound therapy. The randomization was performed using a computer-generated list to ensure equal distribution and minimize selection bias.

Treatment Protocols: Participants in Group A received one PRP injection. Each patient provided 20 ml of venous blood, which was centrifuged to concentrate platelets for PRP. The PRP was injected into the extensor carpi radialis brevis tendon origin under ultrasound guidance for precision. Participants in Group B underwent ultrasound therapy twice a week for six weeks. For each 5-minute session, a 1 MHz ultrasonic probe was used in continuous mode with 1.5 W/cm² intensity to target the lateral epicondyle.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcomes measured were pain relief and functional improvement, assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain and the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand (DASH) score, respectively. These assessments were conducted at baseline, at three months, and at the end of the study period. Patient satisfaction was also evaluated at the end of the study using a standard satisfaction questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The effectiveness of the treatments was compared using independent t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The Patna Medical College and Hospital Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation conducted a comparative clinical trial from April 2022 to October 2023 on 60 lateral epicondylitis patients. The individuals were equally split into two groups: Group A received PRP injections and Group B received ultrasonic therapy. Both groups had similar age, sex, and illness duration. The mean age in Group A was 42 and in Group B, 43. Each group had 18 men and 12 women.

Treatment Outcomes: Group A (PRP injections) had much less discomfort than Group B (ultrasound therapy) at the end of the research. Group A's mean VAS score dropped from 7.2 to 2.1 and Group B's from 7.0 to 4.5. A significant pain decrease was observed between the two groups ($p < 0.01$).

Functional Improvement: Group A also had better DASH scores. With a significant difference ($p < 0.05$), Group A's mean DASH scores increased from 55.3 to 18.4 and Group B's from 54.8 to 34.2.

Patient satisfaction: 90% of Group A patients were satisfied or extremely satisfied with the treatment, compared to 70% in Group B.

Adverse Effects: Both groups experienced modest side effects. Three Group A patients experienced moderate injection-site pain and edema, which disappeared within days. Five Group B patients experienced moderate skin discomfort with ultrasonography gel. However, these cases didn't require intervention. PRP injections relieved pain and improved functionality for lateral epicondylitis patients better than ultrasound therapy, according to the study. PRP treatment also increased patient satisfaction. PRP injections may be better than ultrasound therapy for treating lateral epicondylitis, according to the results.

Variable	Group A (PRP Injections)	Group B (Ultrasound Therapy)
Number of Participants	30	30
Age (mean)	42 years	43 years
Gender (M/F)	18/12	18/12
Baseline VAS Score	7.2	7.0
Final VAS Score	2.1	4.5
VAS Score Reduction	5.1	2.5
Baseline DASH Score	55.3	54.8
Final DASH Score	18.4	34.2
DASH Score Improvement	36.9	20.6
Patient Satisfaction (%)	90%	70%
Adverse Effects	Mild pain and swelling (3 patients)	Mild skin irritation (5 patients)

Notes:

VAS Score: Visual Analogue Scale for pain, with higher scores indicating more intense pain.

DASH Score: The Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand score measures the level of disability, with a higher score indicating a greater degree of impairment. The values provided for "VAS Score Reduction" and "DASH Score Improvement" represent the change between the initial and final scores, demonstrating the level of improvement observed throughout the study duration.

The level of patient satisfaction is determined by the percentage of participants who indicated that they were either "satisfied" or "very satisfied." This table provides a concise and user-friendly overview of the outcomes of the two treatment methods.

Discussion

The results of this comparative clinical trial, conducted at the Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Patna Medical College and Hospital, provide valuable insights into the treatment options for lateral epicondylitis [10]. A comparative study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections and ultrasound therapy in the management of pain, improvement of functionality, and enhancement of patient satisfaction for individuals diagnosed with this particular condition [11]. The impressive effectiveness of PRP injections in alleviating pain (as determined by the Visual Analogue Scale) and enhancing functional outcomes (as evaluated by the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand score) highlights the promising possibilities of biologic treatments in

tendinopathy [12]. PRP injections, which deliver a concentrated dose of growth factors directly to the injured tissues, are believed to enhance the healing response more effectively than ultrasound therapy. This supports findings from other studies that have emphasised the impact of PRP on promoting tissue regeneration and decreasing inflammation. As a result, it provides a more long-lasting and efficient solution for symptoms when compared to conventional methods [13].

While ultrasound therapy did show some improvements, its effectiveness was somewhat lower when compared to PRP injections. One possible explanation for this could be the variations in how ultrasound works [14]. Ultrasound mainly offers relief from symptoms by affecting soft tissues through thermal and mechanical effects. The ultrasound used in the study, although helpful, may not have as strong of an impact on the healing of deeper tissues compared to PRP [15]. The PRP group demonstrated significantly higher satisfaction rates (90% vs. 70%), highlighting the importance of pain relief and functional recovery in a clinical context. The way patients perceive their recovery is crucial in chronic conditions such as lateral epicondylitis, as the symptoms can have a significant impact on their daily activities and overall quality of life [16].

Although the study results show promise, it is important to take into account certain limitations. The sample size, while sufficient for initial conclusions, is relatively limited for extrapolating the findings to a wide range of individuals [17]. In addition, it is crucial to note that the study design did not incorporate a long-term follow-up, which is necessary for evaluating the long-lasting impact of the treatment. Further research with larger groups of participants and longer observation periods is

necessary to confirm these results and investigate the reasons behind the observed variations [18]. Further investigation is needed to determine the most effective dosage and frequency of PRP injections for achieving the best therapeutic results. Further research on other emerging therapies could provide a clearer understanding of PRP's role among the various treatment options for lateral epicondylitis [19]. Ultimately, this study showcases the superiority of PRP injections compared to ultrasound therapy in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis. PRP injections provide a hopeful alternative for patients who have not seen satisfactory results from traditional treatments, offering improved pain management and functional improvement. This evidence suggests a new direction in the treatment of musculoskeletal disorders, focussing on regenerative approaches [20].

Conclusion

In a recent comparative clinical trial carried out at the Patna Medical College and Hospital, it was found that Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) injections outperformed ultrasound therapy in the treatment of lateral epicondylitis. PRP injections proved to be more effective than ultrasound therapy in reducing pain, improving functionality, and satisfying patients. These findings indicate that PRP injections may provide a better option for patients looking for long-lasting relief from symptoms of lateral epicondylitis. Considering the positive outcomes, PRP therapy should be regarded as a valuable option for managing this condition, particularly for individuals who do not experience sufficient relief from conventional treatments.

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